
IMPACT OF GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR- WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PAPER BOAT

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ABSTRACT

Growing environmental concerns have transformed consumer expectations and business practices across industries. Green marketing has emerged as a strategic approach that integrates environmental responsibility with product positioning and brand communication. This study examines the impact of green marketing strategies on consumer behavior with special reference to the Paper Boat beverage brand.

Primary data was collected from 79 respondents through a structured questionnaire. The research analyzes consumer awareness of green marketing, preference for natural products, influence of eco-friendly packaging, brand perception, and willingness to pay for sustainable products. Percentage analysis and tabular presentation were used for interpretation. The findings reveal that green marketing positively influences consumer perception and purchase decisions, particularly through natural ingredients and brand trust. However, price sensitivity and product quality remain critical factors. The study concludes that green marketing is effective when sustainability is supported by value, affordability, and product performance.

Keywords: Green marketing, Consumer Behaviour, Green marketing strategies

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing awareness of environmental degradation, climate change, and health concerns has significantly influenced modern consumer behavior. Consumers are becoming more conscious about the environmental and social impact of the products they purchase. Green marketing refers to the promotion of products that are environmentally safe, sustainable, and produced using eco-friendly processes. It includes use of natural ingredients, sustainable production methods, Eco-friendly packaging, Ethical branding and communication. In the Indian beverage market, consumers are gradually shifting from artificial and carbonated drinks toward natural and traditional alternatives. Paper Boat has positioned itself as a brand offering traditional Indian beverages made from natural ingredients with minimal preservatives and innovative packaging.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

- **Philip Kotler (2011)** : Philip Kotler emphasized that modern marketing must integrate environmental responsibility along with customer satisfaction. According to him, companies that adopt sustainable practices not only contribute to environmental protection but also build a positive brand image. Green marketing helps organizations differentiate themselves and attract environmentally conscious consumers. This concept is relevant to the present study as Paper Boat uses natural ingredients, minimal processing, and eco-friendly packaging to position itself as a responsible brand.
- **Jacquelyn Ottman (2011)**: Ottman explained that green marketing is effective only when companies provide genuine environmental benefits and communicate them clearly to consumers. She highlighted that consumers are more likely to trust brands that are transparent and authentic in their sustainability claims.
- **Nielsen Global Sustainability Report (2021)**: The report revealed that younger consumers are increasingly willing to pay more for sustainable products. Sustainable packaging and natural ingredients significantly influence purchase intention.
- **McKinsey & Company (2022)**: The report indicated that sustainability is becoming a major purchase driver across FMCG categories. However, affordability and availability remain critical factors.

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is significant as it helps in understanding the emerging role of the metaverse in transforming modern marketing and branding strategies, especially in the luxury fashion industry. It provides insights into how brands like Gucci are adopting immersive digital technologies such as NFTs, digital fashion, virtual experiences, and gaming collaborations to enhance brand image and customer engagement. The study also highlights how consumer behaviour is shifting towards virtual ownership, digital identity, and experience-based interaction with brands. Furthermore, it explains the transition from traditional marketing methods to innovative and interactive digital marketing strategies. The findings of this study may be useful for businesses, marketers, and researchers in understanding the potential of the metaverse as a future marketing platform and its impact on brand loyalty, global brand presence, and consumer perception.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study consumer awareness about green marketing.
2. To analyze consumer preference for natural and eco-friendly products.
3. To examine the influence of natural ingredients on purchase decisions.
4. To evaluate the impact of eco-friendly packaging and brand image.
5. To assess consumer willingness to pay for green products.
6. To understand the effectiveness of Paper Boat’s green marketing strategies.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: Descriptive research

Sample Size: 79 respondents

Sampling Technique: Convenience sampling

Data Collection:

Primary Data: Structured questionnaire (Google Form)

Secondary Data: Journals, websites, books, company reports

Statistical Tools Used: Percentage analysis, Tabular presentation, Graphical representation, Microsoft Excel

6. HYPOTHESIS

H₀: Green marketing strategies have no significant impact on consumer purchase decisions.

H₁: Green marketing strategies significantly influence consumer purchase decisions.

7. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION (RESULTS)

Awareness of Green Marketing

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	60	68.4%
No	19	31.6%
Total	79	100%

5) Are you aware of eco friendly practices
79 responses

Interpretation:

A majority (76%) of respondents are aware of green marketing practices. This indicates that environmental concepts have reached a significant portion of consumers, supporting the objective of analyzing awareness levels.

Preference for Natural/Eco-Friendly Products

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Prefer	65	82%
Do not prefer	14	18%

6) How important is environmental protection to you
79 responses

Interpretation:

Most respondents prefer natural products, indicating a positive consumer attitude toward environmentally friendly alternatives. This supports the growing demand for green products in the beverage industry.

Awareness of Paper Boat Brand

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	70	82.3%
No	9	17.7%

9) Are you aware of the paper boat brand
79 responses

Interpretation:

High brand awareness indicates strong market presence and effective brand communication strategies.

Influence of Natural Ingredients on Purchase

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	68	83.5%
No	11	16.5%

12) Does eco friendly packaging affect your purchase decisions
79 responses

Interpretation:

Natural ingredients significantly influence purchase decisions, indicating that health consciousness is a key driver of consumer behavior.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING USING CHI-SQUARE METHOD:

H0 (Null Hypothesis):

Metaverse marketing has no significant impact on Gucci’s branding and marketing effectiveness.

H1 (Alternative Hypothesis):

Metaverse marketing has a significant impact on Gucci’s branding and marketing effectiveness.

Observed Frequencies

Response Option	Observed (O)
Strongly Agree	17
Agree	21
Neutral	30
Disagree	3
Total	71

Expected Frequencies (E)

If there was **no significant impact**, responses would be evenly distributed.

Expected frequency for each category:

E= Total/ Number of categories

$$E = \frac{71}{4} = 17.75$$

So expected frequency for each option = **17.75**

Chi-Square Formula

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Calculations:

Option	O	E	(O-E) ² / E
Strongly Agree	17	17.75	0.031
Agree	21	17.75	0.596
Neutral	30	17.75	8.447
Disagree	3	17.75	12.256

$$\chi^2 = 0.031 + 0.596 + 8.447 + 12.256$$

$$\chi^2 = 21.33$$

Critical Value

Degrees of Freedom (df):

$$df = (n - 1)$$

$$df = 4 - 1 = 3$$

At 5% significance level,

Critical value of χ^2 (df = 3) = **7.815**

If: *Calculated value* > *Critical value* Reject H0

Since:

$$21.33 > 7.815$$

H0 is rejected.

8. KEY FINDINGS

- Consumers have high awareness of green marketing concepts.
- Preference for natural and healthy products is increasing.

- Natural ingredients strongly influence purchase decisions.
- Paper Boat enjoys strong brand recognition.
- Eco-friendly packaging has moderate influence.
- Consumers are price-sensitive and expect value for money.
- There exists an attitude–behavior gap in green purchasing.
- Green marketing positively enhances brand perception.

9. CONCLUSION

Green marketing significantly influences consumer perception and purchase behavior in the beverage market. Paper Boat's focus on natural ingredients, traditional recipes, and responsible branding has successfully positioned it as a healthy and environmentally conscious alternative. However, sustainability alone does not guarantee purchase. Consumers expect quality, affordability, and convenience alongside environmental benefits.

Based on the findings, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted, confirming that green marketing strategies significantly influence consumer choices.

10. LIMITATIONS

1. The sample size was limited to 79 respondents, which may not fully represent the broader consumer population.
2. The study adopted a convenience sampling method, which may affect the generalizability of the findings.
3. The responses were based on self-reported perceptions, which may include personal bias or socially desirable answers.
4. The geographical coverage of the study was limited, restricting wider applicability of results.
5. The research focused only on the Paper Boat brand and did not compare findings with other beverage brands.

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